

of test and reference solution was observed at 570 nm, which was used for spectrophotometric determinations (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra: (A) chromotrope 2B dye against water, and (B) chromotrope 2B dye + thorium against water.

The optimum pH for maximum color development was found in the range 2.5–3.0. At lower pH the dye was liberated even without the addition of fluoride and at higher pH the dye was not liberated at all. The reaction was rapid at room temperature. No change was observed upto 15–40°. The liberated dye was found to be stable for ~12 h. Absorbance values were maximum at molar ratio 1 : 1 of 0.002 M dye and 0.001 M thorium solutions.

Beer's law, determination limit and reproducibility: Beer's law is obeyed in the range 2.5–20 μg of fluoride per 10 ml. Reproducibility was checked by determining 10 μg of fluoride per 10 ml, over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.01 and 1.50%, respectively.

It was found that sodium, potassium, nitrate, nitrite and chloride do not interfere. Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Al^{III} which also form complexes with fluoride, interfere, which are removed by cation-exchange resins. Sulphates can be removed after precipitation as recommended¹⁸. However, most of the interferences are removed by distillation of fluoride prior to its determination as recommended¹¹.

Application of method: The method was applied for the determination of fluoride in drinking water and waste water. Waste water sample of fluoride contained a number of interfering anions and cations along with sulphate. It was therefore necessary to separate the fluoride by distillation¹¹ prior to analysis by the present method and SPADNS method. The results presented in Table I are in close agreement.

Conclusion: The present method is sensitive, rapid and easy to carry out. It can be successfully applied for the determination of fluoride in drinking and polluted river water.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF FLUORIDE IN POLLUTED RIVER WATER*

Sample no.	Fluoride found (Present method)	Fluoride found (SPADNS method)
	μg	μg
1.	9.2	9.0
2.	13.5	14.0
3.	22.0	22.5
4.	18.0	18.0
5.	5.3	5.0

*Sample of river water collected near the fertiliser factory was used after distillation.

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An Improved Lindemann Method for Colorimetric Determination of Inorganic Phosphate in Biological Samples

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THE Fiske–Subbarow method¹ for the quantitative determination of inorganic phosphate suffers from the lack of stability of the blue colour of the reduced phosphomolybdate complex. The method was modified by Lindemann² using a combination of hydrazine sulphate and stannous chloride, by Martland and Robison³ using quinols in sodium

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sulphate and by Ames⁵ using ascorbic acid as the reductant. Further modifications were carried out by Delory⁴ and King⁵, and the latter has been successfully used by Khan and Rao⁶.

One of the common reductants, hydrazine sulphate which provides the most stable complex, has been classified as being carcinogenic and toxic to humans at 7.7 μ M. In the light of this knowledge and the need to obtain phosphomolybdate complex with consistent stability, the search for an alternative reducing combination was necessary. This paper reports a modified method using sodium ascorbate and stannous chloride as the reductants. Effects of different concentrations of ascorbate, buffers and ATPase enzymes from wheat and oat on the stability of the colour with time are described.

Experimental

Solution A was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate (3.55 mmol) in 1.6 N H₂SO₄, solution B dissolving hydrazine sulphate (15.35 mmol) and SnCl₂ (2.22 mmol) in 0.6 N H₂SO₄, and solution C dissolving sodium ascorbate (15.37 mmol) and SnCl₂ (2.22 mmol) in 0.6 N H₂SO₄.

Procedure: To a standard solution (5 ml) of inorganic phosphate or a biological sample containing inorganic phosphate was added solution A (3 ml), followed by either solution B or solution C (2 ml). The mixture was incubated at 22°. The absorbance of the reduced phosphomolybdate complex was measured at 680 nm and at different time intervals after the addition of the reducing agents.

Results and Discussion

Substitution of hydrazine sulphate by ascorbate did not result in either the sensitivity of the method or the limits of detection of orthophosphate being altered (Fig. 1). Further storage of the ascorbate/SnCl₂ reagent for 24 h or doubling the final concentration of the ascorbate to 30.74 mmol had no effect on the sensitivity of the method. There were no changes whether the incubation was carried out in diffuse light or in the dark, suggesting that diffuse light did not alter the reducing potential of ascorbic acid. These findings are significant since previous workers suggested that the incubation must be carried out in the dark when ascorbic acid is used², and that ascorbic acid solutions must always be freshly made⁵. Our findings suggest that the reduction can be carried out in normal laboratory conditions, where there is diffuse light and that the reductant may be prepared the previous day, if necessary.

The reaction was linear within the range of 0–1 μ mole orthophosphate and the blue colour developed within 45 min remained stable for upto 6 h (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2 shows time course studies of the stability of the reduced phosphomolybdate complex from standard inorganic phosphate and phosphate

Fig. 1. Standard curve for inorganic orthophosphate determined using SnCl₂ with hydrazine sulphate (open symbols) or ascorbate (closed symbols) as the reducing agent at 1 h (circles) and 3 h (triangles) after the addition of the reagent.

released from the hydrolysis of ATP by the Ca-ATPase and 'background' ATPase enzyme systems from microsomal fractions of wheat and oat. The results showed the following. (i) When standard inorganic phosphate was assayed, the intensity of

Fig. 2. Time course for absorbance at 680 nm of the reduced phosphomolybdate complex from (a) high (closed circles) and low (open circles) concentrations of standard orthophosphate, (b) phosphate released from ATP due to the activity of Ca-ATPase from oat (open triangles) and wheat (closed triangles); and (c) 'background' ATPase activity from oat (open squares) and wheat roots (closed squares).

the blue colour remained constant during 1–6 h after the addition of the reductants, and then

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showed a small decrease from 6 to 24 h. (ii) When the phosphate released by Ca-ATPase enzyme systems from wheat and oat were assayed, intensity of the blue colour remained constant during 1–3 h after addition of the reductants, and then the intensity decreased in case of wheat but increased in oat. This increase in colour intensity in the oat system was particularly marked and was attributed to hydrolysis of unreacted ATP when incubated for a long period of time under the acidic conditions. The difference in results between wheat and oat can be attributed to the differences in ATPase activities, which was greater in wheat than oat^{9,10}, thus resulting in less unreacted ATPase being available in the incubation mixture containing the wheat enzyme than the oat system. (iii) The blue phosphomolybdate complex formed by reaction with the phosphate released from 'background' ATPase activities from wheat and oat, was stable for 1–3 h after addition of the reductants, but the intensity increased very sharply after 6 h. This confirms our earlier suggestion that these increases in intensity, which appear only in the biological systems with added ATP may be due to the production of further phosphate by ATP hydrolysis on prolonged incubation under acidic conditions.

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